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CHARACTERIZATIONS AND APPLICATIONS OF NON-POSITIVE PARAMETRIC MECHANICAL METAMATERIALS

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1. Mechanical metamaterials

Metamaterials are human-made architected/composite materials with tailored, extreme, or even qualitatively unprecedented mechanical properties which are mainly determined by rationally designed structures rather than chemical composition /constituent materials.

Rational structural design & proper choices of bulk materials

Lightweight, rigid, strength and multi-functional materials have always been the goal of materials and engineering science. This topic expands the multi-functional applications of mechanical metamaterials based on the characterizations of their unprecedented mechanical properties. ³

(1). Ultralight, ultrastiff, ultrastrong

Structural density 0.9 mg/cm^3 , air density 1.2 mg/cm^3

X. Zheng, et al. *Science* 2014, 344, 1373.

Stretch-dominated to bend-dominated lattices

T. A. Schaedler, et al. *Science* 2011, 334, 962.

Ultralight octahedral hollow-tube microlattices

Ultralight, ultrastiff mechanical metamaterials

Relative density increasing: from recoverable to partially recoverable to completely irrecoverable

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Strong, lightweight, and recoverable three-dimensional ceramic nanolattices

L. R. Meza, et al. *Science* 2014, 345, 1322

(1). Ultralight, ultrastiff, ultrastrong

High strength and recoverability

Alloy-polymer composite nanolattices

X. Zhang, et al. *Nano Lett.* **2018**, *18*, 4247.

J. Bauer, et al. *Nat. Mater.* **2016**, *15*, 438.

Ultra-strong glassy carbon nanolattices

(1). Ultralight, ultrastiff, ultrastrong

Low density material: shellular

S. C. Han, et al. *Adv. Mater.* **2015**, *27*, 5506.

L. R. Meza, et al. *PNAS. USA.* **2015**, *112*, 11502.

Multicore-shell 3D printing

J. Mueller, et al. *Adv. Mater.* **2018**, *30*, 1705001.

X. Zheng, et al. *Nat. Mater.* **2016**, *15*, 1100.

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3D hierarchical architected metamaterials

2. Negative Poisson's ratio (NPR)

Lakes: Foam structures with a NPR

Bending mechanisms of 2D truss structures

The extensive study of NPR structures began in 1987.

R. Lakes, *Science* **1987**, 235, 1038.

Re-entrant hexagonal honeycomb

R. F. Almgren, et al. *J. Elasticity*. **1985**, 15, 427.

Poisson's ratios depend on specific directions

Type a

Type c

Type e

auxetic

Concave - NPR
Convex - PPR

Re-entrant star honeycomb

P. S. Theocaris, et al. *Arch. Appl. Mech.* **1997**, 67, 274.

Re-entrant quadrilateral honeycomb

U.D.Larsen, et al. *Micro. Electro. Mech. Syst.* **1996**, 6, 99.

2. Negative Poisson's ratio (NPR)

2D NPR structures with rotating mechanisms

J.N.Grima, et al., *Adv. Mater.* **2000**, 12, 1912.

A.Spadoni, et al., *J. Mech. Phys. Solids.* **2012**, 60, 156.

S.Jacobs, et al., *Smart. Mater. Struct.* **2012**, 21,075013.

2D NPRs induced by elastic instabilities

K. Bertoldi, et al., *Adv. Mater.* **2010**, 22, 361.

Chiral triangular/quadrangular NPR structures

2. Negative Poisson's ratio (NPR)

3D auxetic NPR mechanical metamaterials

elastic joints and stiff beams or walls

3D printed dual-material auxetic metamaterials

K.Wang, et al. *Mater. Des.* 2015, 67, 159.

Interlocking assembly method

2D NPR truss structures plus symmetric topology

L. Yang, et al. *Int. J. Solids. Struct.* 2015, 69, 475.

X.Wang, et al. *Mater. Des.* 2016, 99, 467.

2. Negative Poisson's ratio (NPR)

Composite 3D auxetic textile structure

Z. Ge, et al. Smart Mater. Struct. 2013, 22, 275.

Indirect additive manufacturing: inkjet 3D printing of wax and metal casting

J. Mun, et al. J. Manuf. Process. 2015, 17, 28.

2. Negative Poisson's ratio (NPR)

J. Schwerdtfeger, et al. *Phys. Status Solidi B*. 2012, 249, 1347.

M. Fu, et al. *Phys. Status Solidi B*. 2016, 253, 1565.

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Q.Gao, et al. *Mater. Des.* 2018, 139, 380.

X.Wang, et al. *Com. Sci. Tech.* 2018, 164, 92.

S. Babae, et al. *Adv. Mater.* 2013, 25, 5044.

3D Soft auxetic metamaterials by elastic instabilities

Kirigami

J. N. Grima, et al. *Adv. Mater.* 2016, 28, 385.

Origami

M. Schenk, S. D. Guest, *P. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* .2013,110,3276.

2. Negative Poisson's ratio (NPR)

Rectangular, square, parallelogram and parallelogram-like structures

Parallely connecting NPR and PPR unit cells

S.D. Broccolo, S.Laurenzi, F. Scarpa. *Compos. Struct*, 2017

Thin plate parts and connected hexagonal components

J. Huang et al. *Compos. Part. B*. 2016, 89, 67.

3. Negative stiffness (NS)

M. Vangbo, et al.
Sens. Actuators. A. Phys. **1998**, 69, 212.

Compressed bistable buckled beam

J. Qiu, et al. *J. Microelectromech. S.* **2004**, 13, 137.

Multi-stable lattice structure made by bistable laminates

F. Dai, et al. *Compos. Struct.* **2013**, 97, 56.

3. Negative stiffness (NS)

Snapping mechanical metamaterials

A. Rafsanjani, et al. *Adv. Mater.* 2015, 27, 5931.

B. Haghpanah, et al. *Adv. Mater.* 2016, 28, 7915.

3. Negative stiffness (NS)

3. Negative stiffness (NS)

Reusable light-weight shock absorbers

C. Ha, et al. *Mater. Des.* **2018**, 141, 426.

T. Frenzel, et al. *Adv. Mater.* **2016**, 28, 5865.

C. Findeisen, et al. *J. Mech. Phys. Solids.* **2017**, 102, 151.

3. Negative stiffness (NS)

Temperature-dependent snapping sequence

C.

Temperature (°C)	Snapping sequence	Configurations
$T < 31$	L4-L3-L2-L1	0000, 0001, 0011, 0111, 1111
$31 < T < 41$	L4-L2-L3-L1	0000, 0001, 0101, 0111, 1111
$41 < T < 46$	L2-L4-L3-L1	0000, 0100, 0101, 0111, 1111
$46 < T < 62$	L2-L4-L1-L3	0000, 0100, 0101, 1101, 1111
$T > 62$	L2-L1-L4-L3	0000, 0100, 1100, 1101, 1111

Deterministic deformation sequence

K. Che, et al. *J. Appl. Mech.* **2017**, 81, 011004.

K. Che, et al. *Soft. Matter.* **2018**, 14, 2492.

3. Negative stiffness (NS)

I. Malik, et al. *J. Mech. Phys. Solids*. 2017, 102, 224.

L. Wu, et al. *Adv. Eng. Mater.* 2018, 20, 1700599.

W. Hu, et al. *Int. J. Mech. Sci.* 2018, 144, 10.

3. Zero stiffness (ZS)

T. Le, K. Ahn, *J. Sound. Vib.* 2011, 330, 6311.

B. Fulcher, et al. *J. Vib. Acoust.* 2014, 136, 031009.

Passive vibration and shock isolators

Parallely connecting NS and positive stiffness elements

4. 3D hierarchical metamaterials with tailored PR

H. Yang, et al. *Comp. Struct.* 2019, 214, 359.

Corresponding 3D hierarchical structures in references

Building blocks of second order hierarchical structures

Primary honeycomb	Secondary honeycomb	Building block	ZPR	PPR	NPR
			(1,1)	(1,2)	(1,3)
			(2,1)	(2,2)	(2,3)
			(3,1)	(3,2)	(3,3)
			(4,1)	(4,2)	(4,3)
			(5,1)	(5,2)	(5,3)

4. 3D hierarchical metamaterials with tailored PR

4. 3D hierarchical metamaterials with tailored PR

Samples of hierarchical structures

Experiments and simulations

4. 3D hierarchical metamaterials with tailored PR

The distribution of deformation of NPR and PPR materials caused by boundary effect.

Theoretical, experimental and FE results of 3D DVH

4. 3D hierarchical metamaterials with tailored PR

Secondary honeycomb	Primary honeycomb		ZPR	PPR	NPR
	Poisson's ratio				
	$\nu_{xz} = 0.01/0, \nu_{zx} = 0.01/0$ $\nu_{yz} = 0.01/0, \nu_{zy} = 0.01/0$ $\nu_{yx} = 0.01/0, \nu_{xy} = 0.01/0$	$\nu_{xz} = 0.01/0, \nu_{zx} = 0.01/0$ $\nu_{yz} = 0.01/0, \nu_{zy} = 0.01/0$ $\nu_{yx} = 0.92/0.95, \nu_{xy} = 1.09/1.04$	$\nu_{xz} = 0.01/0, \nu_{zx} = 0.01/0$ $\nu_{yz} = 0.01/0, \nu_{zy} = 0.01/0$ $\nu_{yx} = -1.12/-1.08, \nu_{xy} = -0.94/-0.96$		
	$\nu_{xz} = 0.85/0.90, \nu_{zx} = 1.18/1.20$ $\nu_{yz} = 0.85/0.90, \nu_{zy} = 1.18/1.20$ $\nu_{yx} = -0.93/-0.96, \nu_{xy} = -0.93/-0.94$	$\nu_{xz} = 0.69/0.75, \nu_{zx} = 0.24/0.46$ $\nu_{yz} = 0.61/0.65, \nu_{zy} = 0.28/0.34$ $\nu_{yx} = 0.52/0.49, \nu_{xy} = 0.47/0.61$	$\nu_{xz} = 0.48/0.54, \nu_{zx} = 0.41/0.46$ $\nu_{yz} = 0.40/0.52, \nu_{zy} = 0.38/0.44$ $\nu_{yx} = -0.68/-0.72, \nu_{xy} = -0.72/-0.70$		
	$\nu_{xz} = -1.10/-1.13, \nu_{zx} = -0.89/-1.02$ $\nu_{yz} = -1.10/-1.13, \nu_{zy} = -0.89/-1.02$ $\nu_{yx} = -0.90/-0.93, \nu_{xy} = -0.90/-0.93$	$\nu_{xz} = -0.61/-0.56, \nu_{zx} = -0.22/-0.34$ $\nu_{yz} = -0.63/-0.64, \nu_{zy} = -0.31/-0.36$ $\nu_{yx} = 0.49/0.54, \nu_{xy} = 0.42/0.52$	$\nu_{xz} = -0.45/-0.56, \nu_{zx} = -0.44/-0.51$ $\nu_{yz} = -0.37/-0.44, \nu_{zy} = -0.26/-0.31$ $\nu_{yx} = -0.71/-0.76, \nu_{xy} = -0.86/-0.90$		
	$\nu_{xz} = 0.92/0.95, \nu_{zx} = 1.15/1.12$ $\nu_{yz} = 0.92/0.95, \nu_{zy} = 1.15/1.12$ $\nu_{yx} = -0.87/-0.89, \nu_{xy} = -0.87/-0.88$	$\nu_{xz} = 0.66/0.64, \nu_{zx} = 0.25/0.38$ $\nu_{yz} = 0.60/0.58, \nu_{zy} = 0.26/0.35$ $\nu_{yx} = 0.34/0.45, \nu_{xy} = 0.42/0.47$	$\nu_{xz} = 0.57/0.52, \nu_{zx} = 0.39/0.41$ $\nu_{yz} = 0.62/0.58, \nu_{zy} = 0.32/0.40$ $\nu_{yx} = -0.80/-0.84, \nu_{xy} = -0.91/-0.86$		
	$\nu_{xz} = -1.20/-1.12, \nu_{zx} = -0.80/-0.84$ $\nu_{yz} = -1.20/-1.12, \nu_{zy} = -0.80/-0.84$ $\nu_{yx} = -0.85/-0.88, \nu_{xy} = -0.85/-0.88$	$\nu_{xz} = -0.64/-0.57, \nu_{zx} = -0.22/-0.34$ $\nu_{yz} = -0.74/-0.70, \nu_{zy} = -0.31/-0.36$ $\nu_{yx} = 0.49/0.52, \nu_{xy} = 0.42/0.50$	$\nu_{xz} = -0.39/-0.44, \nu_{zx} = -0.50/-0.56$ $\nu_{yz} = -0.31/-0.34, \nu_{zy} = -0.26/-0.31$ $\nu_{yx} = -0.66/-0.68, \nu_{xy} = -0.95/-0.88$		

Secondary honeycomb	Primary honeycomb		ZPR	PPR	NPR	
	Poisson's ratio					
	$\nu_{xz} = \nu_{zx} = 0$ $\nu_{yz} = \nu_{zy} = 0$ $\nu_{yx} = \nu_{xy} = 0$	$\nu_{xz} = \nu_{zx} = 0$ $\nu_{yz} = \nu_{zy} = 0$ $\nu_{yx}, \nu_{xy} > 0$	$\nu_{xz} = \nu_{zx} = 0$ $\nu_{yz} = \nu_{zy} = 0$ $\nu_{yx}, \nu_{xy} < 0$	(1,1)	(1,2)	(1,3)
	$\nu_{xz}, \nu_{zx} > 0$ $\nu_{yz}, \nu_{zy} > 0$ $\nu_{yx}, \nu_{xy} < 0$	$\nu_{xz}, \nu_{zx} > 0$ $\nu_{yz}, \nu_{zy} > 0$ $\nu_{yx}, \nu_{xy} > 0$	$\nu_{xz}, \nu_{zx} > 0$ $\nu_{yz}, \nu_{zy} > 0$ $\nu_{yx}, \nu_{xy} < 0$	(2,1)	(2,2)	(2,3)
	$\nu_{xz}, \nu_{zx} < 0$ $\nu_{yz}, \nu_{zy} < 0$ $\nu_{yx}, \nu_{xy} < 0$	$\nu_{xz}, \nu_{zx} < 0$ $\nu_{yz}, \nu_{zy} < 0$ $\nu_{yx}, \nu_{xy} > 0$	$\nu_{xz}, \nu_{zx} < 0$ $\nu_{yz}, \nu_{zy} < 0$ $\nu_{yx}, \nu_{xy} < 0$	(3,1)	(3,2)	(3,3)

Secondary honeycomb	Primary honeycomb		ZPR	PPR	NPR	
	Relative Young's modulus					
	$E_{xs} = 0.96 \times 10^{-2} / 1.00 \times 10^{-2}$ $E_{ys} = 0.96 \times 10^{-2} / 1.00 \times 10^{-2}$ $E_{zs} = 0.99 \times 10^{-2} / 1.00 \times 10^{-2}$	$E_{xs} = 1.95 \times 10^{-4} / 2.04 \times 10^{-4}$ $E_{ys} = 2.01 \times 10^{-4} / 2.10 \times 10^{-4}$ $E_{zs} = 0.71 \times 10^{-2} / 0.76 \times 10^{-2}$	$E_{xs} = 1.78 \times 10^{-4} / 1.96 \times 10^{-4}$ $E_{ys} = 1.84 \times 10^{-4} / 2.01 \times 10^{-4}$ $E_{zs} = 0.73 \times 10^{-2} / 0.84 \times 10^{-2}$			
	$E_{xs} = 2.03 \times 10^{-4} / 2.14 \times 10^{-4}$ $E_{ys} = 2.03 \times 10^{-4} / 2.14 \times 10^{-4}$ $E_{zs} = 2.11 \times 10^{-4} / 2.20 \times 10^{-4}$	$E_{xs} = 0.80 \times 10^{-4} / 0.85 \times 10^{-4}$ $E_{ys} = 0.84 \times 10^{-4} / 0.89 \times 10^{-4}$ $E_{zs} = 1.13 \times 10^{-4} / 1.70 \times 10^{-4}$	$E_{xs} = 0.64 \times 10^{-4} / 0.68 \times 10^{-4}$ $E_{ys} = 0.68 \times 10^{-4} / 0.69 \times 10^{-4}$ $E_{zs} = 1.68 \times 10^{-4} / 1.75 \times 10^{-4}$			
	$E_{xs} = 1.88 \times 10^{-4} / 2.08 \times 10^{-4}$ $E_{ys} = 1.88 \times 10^{-4} / 2.08 \times 10^{-4}$ $E_{zs} = 2.08 \times 10^{-4} / 2.12 \times 10^{-4}$	$E_{xs} = 0.68 \times 10^{-4} / 0.80 \times 10^{-4}$ $E_{ys} = 0.60 \times 10^{-4} / 0.83 \times 10^{-4}$ $E_{zs} = 1.02 \times 10^{-4} / 1.06 \times 10^{-4}$	$E_{xs} = 0.43 \times 10^{-4} / 0.50 \times 10^{-4}$ $E_{ys} = 0.48 \times 10^{-4} / 0.52 \times 10^{-4}$ $E_{zs} = 1.17 \times 10^{-4} / 1.22 \times 10^{-4}$			
	$E_{xs} = 2.42 \times 10^{-4} / 2.80 \times 10^{-4}$ $E_{ys} = 2.42 \times 10^{-4} / 2.80 \times 10^{-4}$ $E_{zs} = 2.98 \times 10^{-4} / 3.12 \times 10^{-4}$	$E_{xs} = 0.96 \times 10^{-4} / 1.10 \times 10^{-4}$ $E_{ys} = 0.98 \times 10^{-4} / 1.12 \times 10^{-4}$ $E_{zs} = 1.76 \times 10^{-4} / 2.07 \times 10^{-4}$	$E_{xs} = 0.67 \times 10^{-4} / 0.80 \times 10^{-4}$ $E_{ys} = 0.88 \times 10^{-4} / 0.78 \times 10^{-4}$ $E_{zs} = 1.84 \times 10^{-4} / 2.12 \times 10^{-4}$			
	$E_{xs} = 3.68 \times 10^{-4} / 4.24 \times 10^{-4}$ $E_{ys} = 3.68 \times 10^{-4} / 4.24 \times 10^{-4}$ $E_{zs} = 6.64 \times 10^{-4} / 6.08 \times 10^{-4}$	$E_{xs} = 1.04 \times 10^{-4} / 1.14 \times 10^{-4}$ $E_{ys} = 1.00 \times 10^{-4} / 1.12 \times 10^{-4}$ $E_{zs} = 2.50 \times 10^{-4} / 3.00 \times 10^{-4}$	$E_{xs} = 0.83 \times 10^{-4} / 1.00 \times 10^{-4}$ $E_{ys} = 0.85 \times 10^{-4} / 0.93 \times 10^{-4}$ $E_{zs} = 3.60 \times 10^{-4} / 3.22 \times 10^{-4}$			

Experimental/numerical results of Poisson's ratio and relative Young's modulus of the hierarchical structures in x, y and z direction

5. 3D double-U hierarchical auxetic structures (3D DUH)

Samples and compression tests

Mesh convergence

5. 3D double-U hierarchical auxetic structures (3D DUH)

The estimated reduction length and effective length due to the overlapping connections.

5. 3D double-U hierarchical auxetic structures (3D DUH)

The influence of relative density

The influence of unit cells

5. 3D double-U hierarchical auxetic structures (3D DUH)

Quasi-static collapse behavior of the 3D DUH and DVH

6. Multi-stable mechanical metamaterials

Curved-beam bistable mechanism

Multi-stable structures

6. Multi-stable mechanical metamaterials

**Multistable/
shape-reconfigurable
tubes/cylinders**

6. Multi-stable mechanical metamaterials

Multi-stable mechanical metamaterials for shock absorbers and dampers

The end

Thank you!